

Investment in Advanced Medical Equipment in Hospitals Cannot Yet Be Operational Due to the BPJS Funding Scheme

Ibnu Naser Arrohim¹, Nanik Trihastuti²

^{1,2}Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Semarang, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study examines issue of government investment in advanced medical equipment in hospitals collaborating with BPJS Health that cannot yet be fully utilised due to limitations within BPJS funding and insurance coverage scheme. Although government has invested significantly in modernising hospital facilities and improving healthcare services, use of certain advanced medical technologies remains limited because not all procedures or equipment are covered by BPJS Health financing. This research applies a normative legal method by analysing relevant legislation as primary legal source. The study reviews several regulatory frameworks governing health services and BPJS coverage, including Health Act No. 36 of 2009 on Health, Act No. 40 of 2004 on National Social Security System, Law No. 24 of 2011 on the Social Security Administering Body (BPJS), and Presidential Regulation No. 59 of 2024 concerning the Third Amendment to Presidential Regulation No. 82 of 2018 on Health Insurance. In principle, these regulations require hospitals to provide healthcare services and prohibit refusal of patients. However, implementation remains suboptimal. The effective utilisation of government-funded medical equipment within BPJS Health system depends on strengthened healthcare facilities, accreditation, and adequate infrastructure so that advanced technologies can be integrated into services for BPJS participants and improve healthcare delivery.

KEYWORDS: BPJS, Advanced Equipment, Investment, Scheme

I. INTRODUCTION

Social security in Indonesia is enshrined in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, which provides for social welfare for all the people of Indonesia; this forms the foundation upon which the Indonesian state organises social security for its people.¹

The Indonesian Government established a national social security system following the amendments to the 1945 Constitution, which were implemented through Law No. 40 of 2004 on the National Social Security System—hereinafter referred to as the National Social Security System Law—as evidence of the strong commitment of the Government and relevant stakeholders to achieving social welfare for all its people.²

In this regard, the Indonesian government established the Social Security Administration Agency (BPJS) to administer social security programmes in accordance with Law No. 40 of 2004 on the National Social Security System and Law No. 24 of 2011 on the Social Security Administration Agency. The implementation of these two laws led to the formation of two BPJS agencies, one of which is BPJS Health. BPJS Health is a state-owned enterprise specifically tasked by the government with providing health insurance for all Indonesian citizens.³

The Indonesian Social Security System is a government programme that provides social protection to all Indonesian citizens, particularly the disadvantaged and vulnerable. The system aims to improve social welfare and reduce economic inequality within society.⁴

¹ Diah Arimbi, *Konsep Dasar Hukum Penyelenggaraan Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional Di Indonesia*, (Brebes: Wawasan Ilmu, 2022) p.9

² Keysa Meisya Rombot, Ronlad Eirik Rorie, Sarah D. L, Roeroe, *Pembatasan Jaminan Kesehatan 9 Oleh Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial (BPJS) Kesehatan*, Lex Generalis, Unsrat, vol 3 , 2022 p.8.

³ BPJS Kesehatan, BPJS Kesehatan, https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/BPJS_kesehatan, Diakses pada 20 Maret 2026.

⁴ Adellya Salsabila Hermawan, Sondang Sijabat, Dustin Orlando Exaudi Bakara, Danna Muhamad Bagas Abdurrahman, *Tantangan Dan Peluang Dalam Sistem Jaminan Sosial: Analisis Perbandingan Konsep Pembiayaan Dan Manajemen Jaminan Sosial Di Indonesia Dan Singapura*, Diponegoro Law Private Review (DPLR) Vol 9 No. 1 Tahun 2022, p.91

Investment in Advanced Medical Equipment in Hospitals Cannot Yet Be Operational Due to the BPJS Funding Scheme

The establishment of BPJS, in addition to being mandated by Law No. 40 of 2004, is also the fulfilment of the mandate of Article 28H(3) of the 1945 Constitution, which states that every person has the right to social security that enables the holistic development of the individual as a person of dignity. Meanwhile, the state's obligation to develop a social security system for all the people of Indonesia is governed by Article 34(2), which is realised by providing certainty of social protection and welfare in the form of health insurance and employment insurance. These two forms of insurance constitute the core elements of social security.⁵

Social security provides healthcare protection for the public. Social security serves a social function by safeguarding the livelihood of people within society on the basis of social justice.⁶ Social Security is part of the concept of social protection, which is broader in scope.⁷

The Social Security Administration Agency (BPJS) is an institution established to administer social security programmes in Indonesia pursuant to Law No. 40 of 2004 and Law No. 24 of 2011. In accordance with Law No. 40 of 2004 on the National Social Security System, BPJS is a non-profit legal entity. Under Law No. 24 of 2011, BPJS replaced a number of existing social security institutions in Indonesia, namely the health insurance institution PT Askes Indonesia, which became BPJS Health, and the employment social security institution PT Jamsostek, which became BPJS Employment. The transformation of PT Askes and PT Jamsostek into BPJS was carried out in stages. In early 2014, PT Askes became BPJS Health, followed in 2015 by PT Jamsostek becoming BPJS Employment. The agency is accountable to the President. BPJS has its headquarters in Jakarta and may have representative offices at the provincial level as well as branch offices at the regency and city levels. Every Indonesian citizen and foreign national who has resided in Indonesia for at least six months is required to be a member of BPJS.

The legal aspects of the administration of social security from 1947 to 2011 can be outlined as follows:

1. Act No. 33 of 1947 on the Payment of Compensation to Workers Who Have Suffered Accidents Related to Employment.
2. Law No. 2 of 1957 on the Enforcement of Law No. 33 of 1947
3. Minister of Labour Regulation No. 48 of 1952 in conjunction with Minister of Labour Regulation No. 8 of 1956 on the Regulation of Assistance for the Organisation of Workers' Health Services
4. Ministerial Regulation No. 5 of 1964 on the Establishment of the Social Security Fund Foundation (YDJS).
5. Minister of Health Regulation No. 1 of 1968 establishing the Health Maintenance Fund Management Agency (BPDPK), which regulates health maintenance for civil servants and pensioners, as well as their families.
6. Law No. 14 of 1969 on the Fundamentals of Labour, which regulates the provision of social insurance and social assistance for workers and their families
7. Government Regulation No. 33 of 1977 on Social Insurance for Workers.
8. Government Regulations No. 22 and 25 of 1984 on Health Care for Civil Servants and Pensioners and Their Families.
9. Law No. 3 of 1992 on JAMSOSTEK
10. Government Regulation No. 6 of 1992 on the Conversion of the State-Owned Enterprise Husada Bhakti into a State-Owned Limited Liability Company.
11. Law No. 40 of 2004 on the Indonesian National Social Security System, implemented by the Social Security Administration Agency (BPJS) pursuant to Law No. 24 of 2011.⁸

BPJS is a transformation of Jamsostek, specifically since the enactment of the National Social Security System (SJSN Law) on October 19, 2004. This transformation will introduce a new identity to the implementation of social security programs in Indonesia. The BPJS Law established two Social Security Administrative Bodies (BPJS): BPJS Health and BPJS Employment.

BPJS Health provides health insurance for all Indonesian residents, including foreigners working in Indonesia for at least six months. BPJS Employment provides death insurance for all Indonesian workers, including foreigners working in Indonesia for at least six months. Four state-owned enterprises (BUMN) administering social security programs: PT. ASKES (Persero), PT. ASABRI (Persero), PT. JAMSOSTEK (Persero), and PT. TASPEN (Persero) will transform into BPJS. The BPJS Law has designated PT. ASKES (Persero) to transform into BPJS Health, and PT. JAMSOSTEK will transform into BPJS. The law regulates the mechanism for administering work accident insurance, old-age security, pension insurance, and employment programs.

BPJS is the embodiment of a welfare state. A welfare state is a government concept that assumes full responsibility for the social and economic welfare of its citizens, encompassing healthcare, education, and social security, primarily through income redistribution (taxes). This concept aims to create equality, social justice, and a minimum standard of living for the people.

⁵ Pusat Analisis Dan Evaluasi Hukum Nasional Badan Pembinaan Hukum Nasional Kementerian Hukum dan HAM, *Laporan Akhir Kelompok Kerja Analisis Evaluasi Hukum Mengenai Pemenuhan Hak Kesehatan*, (Jakarta :Kemenkumham 2017) p.2

⁶ Diah Arimbi, *Konsep Dasar Hukum Penyelenggaraan Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional di Indonesia*, (Jawa Tengah: Wawasan ilmu, 2022) p.3

⁷ Widodo Suryandono, *Laporan Akhir Tim Analisis dan Evaluasi Undang-undang Nomor 40 Tahun 2004 tentang Sistem jaminan Sosial Nasional*, Badan pembinaan Hukum Nasional, 2011, p.9

⁸ Ibid p.10

Investment in Advanced Medical Equipment in Hospitals Cannot Yet Be Operational Due to the BPJS Funding Scheme

BPJS aims to ensure the fulfillment of basic living needs for every participant and/or their family members. BPJS Health is tasked with providing basic health protection for all Indonesian people, without exception, so that all Indonesians have comprehensive, fair and equitable health insurance without any discrimination, while BPJS Employment is tasked with protecting Indonesian workers, both formal and non-formal workers, by providing pension insurance, old age insurance, work accident insurance, and death insurance. However, both BPJS have similarities, namely imposing contributions on the Indonesian community and workers in accordance with the applicable regulations regarding BPJS.⁹

Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of themselves and their families, including the right to food, clothing, housing, health care, and necessary social services, as well as the right to security in the event of unemployment, illness, disability, abandonment, old age, or other circumstances beyond their control resulting in a decline in their standard of living.

The implementation of the BPJS Health program has not yet achieved the optimal results hoped for by the Indonesian government. While equitable health services are greatly needed by the public, under certain circumstances, health services are not implemented equally. In its implementation, the national health insurance program for the public has not yet achieved its full potential. This is evident in the numerous problems faced by BPJS Health participants, particularly in the use of certain medical devices.

BPJS Health patients, in relation to hospitals, are sick individuals who require medical assistance to treat their illnesses. Patients are subjects who have a significant influence on the outcome of services, not merely objects. As patients in hospitals, their rights must be fulfilled, considering that patient satisfaction is a barometer of service quality in hospitals. Based on Article 32 of Law Number 44 of 2009 concerning hospitals, patient rights in hospitals must be guaranteed.¹⁰

In today's era of globalisation, there are many advanced digital tools with a wide range of functions, designed to meet the needs of people who want to carry out their activities quickly. Various fields, such as those related to technological advancements in knowledge or research, require sophisticated tools to achieve research outcomes.

Advanced tools are modern, high-tech devices designed with complex systems to simplify tasks, enhance efficiency and improve accuracy. These tools often incorporate automation, artificial intelligence or the latest technologies to provide practical solutions across various sectors, such as healthcare, research and everyday life.¹¹

Some healthcare services utilising advanced and state-of-the-art technology in Indonesia are still not covered by BPJS Health or are still in the process of establishing partnerships, including PET-SCAN (Positron Emission Tomography Scan), radiotherapy, the Cath Lab (Cardiac Catheterisation Laboratory), phacoemulsification, and PCOS (Polycystic Ovary Syndrome) screening.

The government provides investment in advanced and modern medical equipment to hospitals collaborating with BPJS; however, in practice, not all of this equipment can be utilised because not all such medical devices are covered by BPJS health insurance.

Based on the background outlined above, the author will investigate government investment in healthcare where not all data is utilised by BPJS service users, under the title: "Investment in Advanced Services (Medical Equipment) in Hospitals That Cannot Yet Operate Due to the BPJS Funding Scheme"

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The method employed in this study is the normative legal approach, which involves using legislation as the subject of analysis. The data collection technique utilised by the researcher in this study is a literature review, whereby data is obtained from academic writings and research published in articles and other journals.

The approach used in this study is the normative legal approach. The legal approach in question views law as a norm or *das sollen*, as the discussion of issues in this study utilises legal materials.¹²

Etymologically, the term 'normative legal research' originates from English; in Dutch it is known as 'normative juridisch onderzoek', whilst in German it is known as 'normative juristische Forschung'.¹³

This study employs a statutory approach and a conceptual approach. The legislation forming the basis of this research includes Law No. 40 of 2004 on the Indonesian National Social Security System and Law No. 24 of 2011 on the Social Security Administration Agency (BPJS Law).

⁹ Fachru Nofrian Bakarudin, Fahmi Wibawa, Ferdi Nggao, Imam Ahmad, Malik Ruslan, Lya Angraini dan Zaenal Muttaqin, *Penjaminan Kesehatan di Indonesia sejarah dan Tranformasi BPJS Kesehatan, 2020*, p.37.

¹⁰ Kesya Meisy Rombot, *Ibid* p.9

¹¹ <https://www.kompas.id/artikel/teknologi-canggih-untuk-meningkatkan-kesehatan> diakses 12 maret 2026 pukul; 19.00 WIB.

¹² Bambang Sugono, *Metode Penelitian Hukum*, (Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, 2006) pp.97- 98.

¹³ Salim HS dan Erlies Septiana Nurbani, *Penerapan Teori Hukum Pada Penelitian Tesis dan Disertasi*, (Jakarta : Raja Grafindo Persada, 2014) p.18

Investment in Advanced Medical Equipment in Hospitals Cannot Yet Be Operational Due to the BPJS Funding Scheme

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

BPJS, or the Social Security Administration Agency, is a legal entity established by the government to administer health insurance programmes with the aim of protecting the entire population through affordable premiums and providing comprehensive services to all Indonesians.

Presidential Regulation (Perpres) No. 59 of 2024 concerning the Third Amendment to Presidential Regulation No. 82 of 2018 on Health Insurance, Article 1(1), 'Health Insurance' refers to insurance in the form of health protection so that participants receive health maintenance benefits and protection in meeting basic health needs, provided to every person who has paid their Health Insurance Contribution or whose Health Insurance Contribution is paid by the Central Government or Local Government.

Healthcare services must be provided to every person in need, whether they pay in cash or through insurance; one of the social insurance schemes in Indonesia is BPJS Health. BPJS Health services focus on primary healthcare or primary healthcare facilities. Using BPJS Health services has become a choice for the Indonesian public because it offers many conveniences for people to access adequate healthcare services at an affordable cost.¹⁴

The BPJS Health funding scheme operates on a mutual social security system, whereby contributions from healthy participants help those who are ill. Funding sources include contributions from self-employed participants (PBPU), contributions from Wage-Earning Workers (PPU) shared between employers and employees (4% + 1%), and government subsidies via the State Budget (APBN) or Regional Budget (APBD) for participants receiving Contribution Assistance (PBI).

For self-employed participants or non-wage-earning workers, contributions are borne by the individual according to class: for Class 1, the contribution is 150,000 per person per month; for Class 2, 100,000 per person per month; and for Class 3, 42,000 per person per month, where Class 3 receives a government subsidy of 7,000 rupiah and the participant pays 35,000.

Pursuant to Article 1(3) of Law No. 40 of 2004 on the National Social Security System (hereinafter referred to as the National Social Security System Law), social insurance is a compulsory fund-raising mechanism derived from contributions to provide protection against socio-economic risks affecting participants and/or their family members.¹⁵

The provision of healthcare services is often prone to maladministration due to the absence of regulations or rules governing how hospitals should treat patients covered by the BPJS Health scheme. The same applies to services for self-paying patients and those with private insurance, as there is no standardised hospital management system in place to ensure that all those in need are treated.

Restrictions on health coverage by healthcare facilities are caused by factors relating to both regulation and the management of those facilities. If a patient is refused treatment on the basis of a quota for BPJS Health participants, this is not permissible as it constitutes discriminatory behaviour and is therefore subject to administrative sanctions.

Restrictions also occur in the form of quota enforcement, leading to discriminatory treatment of BPJS Health patients. The causes include limited capacity and a shortage of doctors, the availability of rooms and medical equipment, as well as differences in funding for healthcare facilities.

Health Law No. 36 of 2006 on Health regulates the refusal of healthcare services by hospitals; specifically, Article 32(2) states that in emergency situations, healthcare facilities—whether government or private hospitals—are prohibited from refusing patients or demanding advance payment.

In principle, legislation does indeed stipulate that hospitals must not refuse patients, as set out in the provisions of the Health Law mentioned above; however, many have yet to comply with these regulations.

There are also restrictions on medicines, as BPJS Health provides healthcare services in accordance with national guidelines and the national formulary (the list of medicines covered by BPJS), meaning not all medicines are covered by BPJS Health, particularly new, expensive medicines or those not included in the formulary. The level and type of service provided are determined according to objective medical needs.

Article 22(1) of Law No. 40 of 2004 states:

"Health insurance benefits consist of individual healthcare services, including promotive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative care, as well as necessary medicines and consumable medical supplies."

The existence of restrictions on BPJS services clearly contradicts the aforementioned Article 22; therefore, service management must be improved to ensure compliance with the provisions of the Health Insurance Law. Safe, high-quality and effective healthcare services, prioritising the interests of BPJS participants in accordance with hospital service standards, must be provided by hospitals to the public, as BPJS participants are entitled to healthcare services.

From the perspective of distributive justice theory, there is a disconnect between the letter of the law and its practical application. Distributive justice is a principle governing the fair distribution of resources, wealth and social benefits within society.

¹⁴ Zulfa, Mualifatus. "Perbedaan Pelayanan Antara Pien Bpjs Dan Pasien Umum.", Skripsi, Universitas KH. Strada Indonesia, (2022). p.1

¹⁵ Wijaya, A. *Hukum Jaminan Sosial Indonesia*. (Jakarta : Sinar Grafika, 2017) p.36

Investment in Advanced Medical Equipment in Hospitals Cannot Yet Be Operational Due to the BPJS Funding Scheme

This principle emphasises that distribution must be based on individual needs, contributions, and efforts. In the context of public law, distributive justice serves as the foundation for designing policies aimed at reducing social and economic inequality.¹⁶

According to Hans Kelsen, the term 'justice' is used in a legal sense to denote conformity with positive law, particularly conformity with legislation.¹⁷ The theory of distributive justice is based on the fulfilment of basic needs such as food, clothing and shelter, which are considered to be the responsibility of the authorities, although this assessment is subjective.

Distributive justice forms the basis for the formulation of a country's social and economic policies. The government has a duty to distribute resources fairly, particularly to ensure equitable access to education and healthcare, social protection for the poor, and fair and decent employment opportunities. An example of this is progressive taxation, whereby high-income earners pay higher taxes to support public services for the entire population.¹⁸

1. Steps Taken by BPJS to Utilise Government Investment (Advanced Services) in Medical Equipment.

Health is the most important issue for the public. To safeguard public health, the government has implemented regulations or policies regarding health insurance, specifically the National Health Insurance (JKN), which is administered by a third-party funding body. This third-party financing refers to funding via health insurance cards, which generates receivables that must be collected by hospitals to meet the costs of medical treatment and healthcare services provided to patients. Receivables should serve as a source of income for hospitals; however, if a significant number of receivables remain uncollected, this will hinder the hospital's financial operations.¹⁹

Social security is regarded as the government's effort to protect the public (or the majority of its members) from economic hardships that may lead to loss of income due to illness, unemployment, disability, old age and death; to provide the public with the necessary healthcare; and to assist families in raising children.²⁰

The National Social Security System is a framework for state and government programmes designed to provide social protection, ensuring that every citizen can meet their basic needs for a decent standard of living, with a view to achieving social welfare for all the people of Indonesia.²¹ The national social security system is essentially a programme designed to provide guaranteed social protection and welfare for all the people of Indonesia. The social security system is also intended as a means of promoting welfare and providing a sense of security throughout a person's life through a systematic approach.²²

The Social Security Administration Agency is a legal entity established to administer social security programmes to ensure that all citizens can meet their basic needs for a decent standard of living. The BPJS operates on the principles of humanity, benefit and social justice for all the people of Indonesia, with the aim of ensuring that every Indonesian citizen's basic needs for a decent standard of living are met, as this constitutes a fundamental human right.²³

The availability of healthcare facilities varies across different regions; some areas have advanced equipment whilst others do not, but even where such equipment is available, it is not necessarily accessible to patients covered by the BPJS scheme. Although the government has made significant investments in healthcare, much of this infrastructure remains idle—meaning the assets are operational but not actively in use (stationary).

Advanced medical equipment is not made available to BPJS participants for several reasons, namely those related to regulations, medical considerations and administration. Common factors include:

1. Does not meet the medical criteria.

¹⁶Stekom.ac.id, [https://stekom.ac.id/artikel/keadilan-distributif-dalam-perspektif-hukum-publik#:~:text=Konsep%20Keadilan%20Distributif,mengurangi%20kesenjangan%20sosial%20dan%](https://stekom.ac.id/artikel/keadilan-distributif-dalam-perspektif-hukum-publik#:~:text=Konsep%20Keadilan%20Distributif,mengurangi%20kesenjangan%20sosial%20dan%20) diakses 28 februari 2016 Pukul 09.00 WIB.

¹⁷ Hans Kelsen, *Pengantar Teori Hukum*, (Jakarta:Nusa Media,) p.47

¹⁸ KPU kab Jaya Wijaya, *Teori-Teori Keadilan Distributif Modern Di Dunia*, Artikel,4 November 2025 [Http://Kab-jayawijaya.kpu.go](http://Kab-jayawijaya.kpu.go). Diakses 28 Februari 2026 Pukul 09.00 wib

¹⁹ Reski Ananda Putri, *Pengelolaan Piutang Pada BPJS Kesehatan Kantor Cabang di Kota Pare-Pare* (Analisis AkuntansiSyatriha), Skripsi, IAIN Pare-Pare, p.68

²⁰ Sentanoe Kertonegoro, *Jaminan Sosial Prinsip dan Pelaksanaanya di Indonesia*, (Jakarta: Mutiara,2006) p.26.

²¹ Anna Febrina Ginting, et al., *Implementasi Program Jaminan Sosial Ketenagakerjaan di Kota Manado*”, *Jurnal Administrasi Publik* Vol. 3 No. 400, 2016, p.1.

²² Sulastomo, *Sistem Jaminan Sosial Nasional Sebuah Introduksi*, (Jakarta : Rajawali Pers, 2008) p.5.

²³ Bunga Tri Amanda; Aditya Yuda Prasetya; Kaharudin; Billy Josef Anis, *Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial (BPJS) Kesehatan Sebagai Strategi Manajemen Berbasis Keadilan Sosial dalam Pelayanan Kesehatan* , Prosiding EMAS: EkonomiManajemen Akuntansi Kewirausahaan Vol.1 No.1 Juni 2021, p.186.

Investment in Advanced Medical Equipment in Hospitals Cannot Yet Be Operational Due to the BPJS Funding Scheme

Medical aids such as glasses and hearing aids are only covered if they are prescribed for a medical condition and recommended by a specialist doctor affiliated with BPJS.

2. Exceeding the limit

BPJS has a ceiling or maximum limit on the cost of medical aids. If the cost of the required aid exceeds this ceiling, the participant must cover the difference themselves.

3. Lack of equipment in healthcare facilities

The healthcare facility does not have this medical device or it is not included in the list of medical devices covered by BPJS Health

4. Referral procedure not followed

Medical devices will not be provided if the BPJS participant does not follow the tiered referral procedure from the Primary Health Care Facility (FKTP) or community health centre (puskesmas) to the referral health facility or hospital.

5. Inactive membership status

Medical devices cannot be claimed if the participant's BPJS membership is inactive or suspended due to arrears of more than three months' contributions or failure to update data for participants receiving contribution assistance (PBI).

6. Devices not intended for basic medical use

Devices of a cosmetic or aesthetic nature, such as the use of dental braces.

The utilisation of government investment in advanced medical equipment within the BPJS Health service is carried out through mechanisms to strengthen healthcare facilities and through credentialing, to ensure that healthcare facilities are capable of providing high-tech medical procedures. This measure aims to ensure access to advanced medical equipment, such as radiotherapy, cardiovascular interventions and others, for health insurance participants.

Accreditation is a process of evaluation, verification, and assessment of suitability carried out on healthcare facilities (faskes) or medical personnel to ensure compliance with quality standards prior to collaborating with BPJS Health. This process includes checks on licences, staff competence, infrastructure, and service track records.

As a step taken to utilise government investment in advanced medical equipment, credentialing and the provision of facilities and infrastructure are required so that government investment in the form of medical equipment can be placed in a hospital and used by BPJS participants; the healthcare facility must meet strict standards. The next step is to submit a credentialing application via the Health Facilities Information System (HFIS) and update the data through this application by the hospital, listing the advanced medical facilities and equipment it possesses. A joint BPJS team and the health department conduct site visits to ensure that the medical equipment purchased by the government or the hospital has been installed, is in working order, and has an SFM (Specialist Medical Technician) or a competent specialist doctor/technician to operate the equipment. Furthermore, healthcare facilities are required to integrate the information system for this advanced medical equipment with the BPJS system for referral or claims purposes.

Government investment in medical equipment is undertaken seriously and prioritises equipment that provides maximum added value. Concurrently, it is hoped that BPJS Health will focus on medical equipment and medicines that are cost-effective and urgently needed by the public, rather than merely advanced. The use of advanced medical equipment is guaranteed provided it complies with medical indications and procedures set out in the Minister of Health's Regulation.

Optimising the JKN mobile app can facilitate doctors in accessing patients' medical histories, including examination results from advanced medical devices. The points outlined above represent the steps that must be taken, with the key measures being strict credentialing within the HFIS, alignment with medical indications, and the digital integration of government-funded medical devices into the BPJS Health referral system to deliver more efficient and modern services.

CONCLUSIONS

The provisions governing health insurance coverage limits by BPJS Kesehatan are set out in the Health Act No. 36 of 2006 on Health, the National Social Security System Act No. 40 of 2004, Law No. 24 of 2011 on BPJS, and Presidential Regulation (Perpres) No. 59 of 2024 on the Third Amendment to Presidential Regulation No. 82 of 2018 on Health Insurance. In principle, legislation does indeed stipulate that hospitals must not refuse patients, as set out in the provisions of the Health Law mentioned above; however, many have yet to comply with these regulations. There are also restrictions on medicines, as BPJS Health provides healthcare services in accordance with national guidelines and the national formulary (the list of medicines covered by BPJS), meaning not all medicines are covered by BPJS Health, particularly new, expensive medicines or those not included in the formulary. The level and type of service provided are determined according to objective medical needs.

A significant amount of government investment in healthcare remains unused and idle; therefore, steps must be taken to activate these resources. Government investment in medical equipment must be undertaken seriously and prioritise equipment that provides maximum added value. At the same time, it is hoped that BPJS Health will focus on medical equipment and medicines

Investment in Advanced Medical Equipment in Hospitals Cannot Yet Be Operational Due to the BPJS Funding Scheme

that are cost-effective and urgently needed by the public, rather than merely advanced. The use of advanced medical equipment is guaranteed provided it is in accordance with medical indications and procedures set out in the Minister of Health's Regulation.

RECOMMENDATION

BPJS should provide a high coverage limit for its members' health insurance so that they can access advanced medical equipment using their BPJS membership contributions

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to express gratitude to colleagues at the Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, for being invaluable discussion partners in the preparation of this journal. The author would like to thank the reviewers and editors for their efforts in shaping this paper.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adellya Salsabila Hermawan, Sondang Sijabat, Dustin Orlando Exaudi Bakara, 2022, Danna Muhamad Bagas Abdurrahman, Tantangan Dan Peluang Dalam Sistem Jaminan Sosial: Analisis Perbandingan Konsep Pembiayaan Dan Manajemen Jaminan Sosial Di Indonesia Dan Singapura, Diponegoro Law Private Review (DPLR) Vol 9 No. 1 Tahun 2022.
- 2) Anna Febrina Ginting, et al., 2016, Implementasi Program Jaminan Sosial Ketenagakerjaan di Kota Manado", Jurnal Administrasi Publik Vol. 3 No. 400
- 3) Bambang Sugono, 2006, Metode Penelitian Hukum, PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta.
- 4) BPJS Kesehatan, BPJS Kesehatan, https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/BPJS_kesehatan
- 5) Bunga Tri Amanda; Aditya Yuda Prasetya; Kaharudin; Billy Josef Anis, Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial (BPJS) Kesehatan Sebagai Strategi Manajemen Berbasis Keadilan Sosial dalam Pelayanan Kesehatan, Prosiding EMAS: Ekonomi Manajemen Akuntansi Kewirausahaan Vol.1 No.1 Juni 2021
- 6) Diah Arimbi, 2022, Konsep Dasar Hukum Penyelenggaraan Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional Di Indonesia, Wawasan Ilmu, Brebes.
- 7) Fachru Nofrian Bakarudin, Fahmi Wibawa, Ferdi Nggao, Imam Ahmad, Malik Ruslan, Lya Angraini dan Zaenal Muttaqin, Penjaminan Kesehatan di Indonesia sejarah dan Transformasi BPJS Kesehatan, BPJS Kesehatan 2020
- 8) Hans Kelsen, Pengantar Teori Hukum, Nusa Media, Jakarta
- 9) <https://www.kompas.id/artikel/teknologi-canggih-untuk-meningkatkan-kesehatan>
- 10) Keysa Meisya Rombot, Ronlad Elrik Rorie, Sarah D. L, Roeroe, Pembatasan Jaminan Kesehatan 9 Oleh Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial (BPJS) Kesehatan, Lex Generalis, Unsrat, Vol 3, 2022
- 11) KPU kab Jaya Wijaya, Teori-Teori Keadilan Distributif Modern Di Dunia, Artikel, 4 November 2025 [Http://Kab-jayawijaya.kpu.go](http://Kab-jayawijaya.kpu.go).
- 12) Peraturan Presiden (Perpres) Nomor 59 Tahun 2024 tentang Perubahan Ketiga atas Peraturan Presiden Nomor 82 Tahun 2018 tentang Jaminan Kesehatan.
- 13) Pusat Analisis Dan Evaluasi Hukum Nasional Badan Pembinaan Hukum Nasional Kementerian Hukum dan HAM, 2017, Laporan Akhir Kelompok Kerja Analisis Evaluasi Hukum Mengenai Pemenuhan Hak Kesehatan, Kemenkumham, Jakarta
- 14) Reski Ananda Putri, Pengelolaan Piutang Pada BPJS Kesehatan Kantor Cabang di Kota Pare-Pare (Analisis Akuntansi Syatriha), Skripsi, IAIN Pare-Pare
- 15) Salim HS dan Erlies Septiana Nurbani, 2014, Penerapan Teori Hukum Pada Penelitian Tesis dan Disertasi, Raja Grafindo Persada, Jakarta
- 16) Sentanoe Kertonegoro, 2006, Jaminan Sosial Prinsip dan Pelaksanaanya di Indonesia, Mutiara, Jakarta.
- 17) Stekom.ac.id, <https://stekom.ac.id/artikel/keadilan-distributif-dalam-perspektif-hukum>
[publik#:~:text=Konsep%20Keadilan%20Distributif,mengurangi%20kesenjangan%20sosial%20dan%](https://stekom.ac.id/artikel/keadilan-distributif-dalam-perspektif-hukum)
- 18) Sulastomo, 2008, Sistem Jaminan Sosial Nasional Sebuah Introduksi, Rajawali Pers, Jakarta
- 19) Undang-Undang Kesehatan Nomor 36 Tahun 2006 tentang Kesehatan
- 20) Undang-Undang No 24 Tahun 2011 tentang Badan penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial
- 21) Undang-Undang Nomor 40 tahun 2004, tentang Sistem Jaminan Sosial Nasional
- 22) Widodo Suryandono, 2011, Laporan Akhir Tim Analisis dan Evaluasi Undang-undang Nomor 40 Tahun 2004 tentang Sistem jaminan Sosial Nasional, Badan Pembinaan Hukum Nasional.
- 23) Wijaya. A, 2017, Hukum Jaminan Sosial Indonesia. Sinar Grafika, Jakarta
- 24) Zulfa, Kualifatus, Perbedaan Pelayanan Antara Pasien BPJS Dan Pasien Umum, Skripsi, Universitas KH. Strada Indonesia, 2022